

BROILER MARKET NEWS REPORT

Friday, August 25, 2023

U.S. Department of Agriculture

Agricultural Marketing Service

Livestock, Poultry & Grain Market News

[National Broiler Market-at-a-Glance](#) - Domestic Market Highlights

Whole broiler/fryer prices are at least steady on whole fryers and firm on wogs. Supplies are light to moderate with 3 pound and heavier wogs in the better position and moving well entering the weekend. Retail and foodservice demand remain light to moderate. Processing schedules are reported as normal. Floor stocks are balanced. Market activity is moderate to active. In the parts structure, prices are trending firm for boneless skinless breast, wings, and tenders with premiums noted. Dark meat prices are steady to firm with leg quarters noted as slightly more available. Supplies of wings, jumbo boneless breast, and tenders are tight to instances short. Demand on the remainder of parts is moderate. Market activity is moderate to active. In production areas, live supplies are moderate. Weights are mixed, but noted as mostly desirable. Export demand remains light to moderate.

[Weekly National Chicken Report](#)

National Chicken, Whole - Cents Per lb

Domestic - Fresh - Conventional - Delivered

	Price Range	Current Week's Trading		1,000 lbs	Previous Week's Trading	
		Wtd Avg	Change		Wtd Avg	1,000 lbs
Nat'l Composite Whole Bird:	74.00 - 150.00	114.85	3.81	11,304	111.04	11,111
WOG						
Trading by Size:						
Nat'l Composite WOGS:	74.00 - 146.00	114.10	3.89	8,406	110.21	7,996
2.50 lb & lighter	89.00 - 137.00	119.46	0.40	1,772	119.06	1,554
2.51 - 3.50 lb	82.00 - 146.00	113.20	4.67	6,491	108.53	6,295
3.51 lb & heavier	74.00 - 96.00	88.26	0.30	143	87.96	145
Whole Body						
Trading by Size:						
Nat'l Composite:	87.00 - 150.00	117.03	3.84	2,897	113.19	3,115
3.00 lb & lighter	110.00 - 149.00	123.17	2.90	661	120.27	525
3.01 lb & heavier	87.00 - 150.00	115.21	3.46	2,236	111.75	2,590

Regional and Specific Destination Pricing:

	Price Range	Current Week's Trading		1,000 lbs	Previous Week's Trading	
		Wtd Avg	Change		Wtd Avg	1,000 lbs
Eastern						
Whole Body:	74.00 - 133.00	113.79	3.64	4,529	110.15	4,629
Eastern WOGS:	74.00 - 133.00	111.48	3.55	2,036	107.93	1,928
New York						
Whole Body	97.00 - 133.00	116.78	4.54	1,855	112.24	1,825
Central						
Whole Body	82.00 - 149.00	107.14	4.49	3,300	102.65	3,072
Central WOGS:	82.00 - 135.00	106.15	4.35	3,135	101.80	2,938
Chicago						
Whole Body	82.00 - 130.00	106.96	3.39	1,799	103.57	1,745
Western						
Whole Body	84.00 - 150.00	123.55	3.74	3,475	119.81	3,410
Western WOGS:	84.00 - 146.00	123.44	3.95	3,235	119.49	3,130
Los Angeles						
Whole Body:	92.00 - 146.00	121.02	2.98	2,505	118.04	2,390

Fresh National Composite Whole Bird Price - Conventional - Delivered

[Weekly Poultry Slaughtered Under Federal Inspection](#) (Preliminary) Week ending 19-Aug-2023

	Young Chickens	Light Hens	Heavy Hens	Total Hens	Duck
----- Thousands -----					
Head	169,385	739	1,968	2,707	498
Avg Wt	6.35	3.55	8.55	7.19	6.94
Head sltr comparisons					
Last week	168,699	665	1,917	2,582	431
Same wk yr ago	170,977	637	1,784	2,421	415
Avg Wt	6.44	3.47	8.41	7.11	6.97
To-date/2023*	5,477,377	24,889	56,150	81,039	14,524
To-date/2022*	5,445,370	22,930	52,842	75,772	14,354
% Change YTD	1%	9%	6%	7%	1%
Ready-to-Cook Weight and Dressing Percentage					
Current week	817,452	1,456	11,526	12,982	2,454
Last week	812,859	1,399	11,109	12,508	2,069
Same wk yr ago	836,830	1,227	10,277	11,504	2,054
To-date/2023*	26,433,963	49,084	322,427	371,511	73,199
To-date/2022*	26,233,749	44,306	300,453	344,759	72,133
% Change YTD	1%	11%	7%	8%	1%

Dressing %	76.0%	55.5%	68.5%		71.0%

(A) The estimated number of fryers available for marketing based on the 2-week revised average chick placements 6 to 7 weeks earlier was 169.3 million head. Estimated U.S. slaughter for this period was 171.4 million head, or 2.1 million more than estimated available.

(B) Dressing % adjustments reflect quarterly update.

*Note: Year to-date totals reflect comparable time periods.

[Weekly Estimated Slaughter of U.S. Broiler/Fryers & Fowl](#)

Class	Current Week	Previous Week
	8/26/2023 (1)	8/19/2023
----- Thousand Head -----		
Broiler/fryer	161,788 (2)	158,677
Light hens	693	719
Heavy hens	1,972	1,983
Total	164,453	161,379

(1) ESTIMATED

(2) The estimated number of broiler-fryers available for slaughter the week ending 26-Aug-23 is 169.3 million head compared to 172.9 million head slaughtered the same week last year. The estimated U.S. slaughter this week is 162.1 million head or -7.2 million less than estimated available. For the week of 02-Sep-23 the estimated available is 168.8 million head.

National Chicken, Parts - Cents Per Lb

Domestic - Fresh - Conventional - FOB

	Price Range	Current Week's Trading			Previous Week's Trading	
		Wtd Avg	Change	1,000 lbs	Wtd Avg	1,000 lbs
Backs and Necks Stripped:	11.00 - 13.00	11.98	-0.16	1,335	12.14	1,473
Breast - B/S:	124.00 - 267.00	149.46	11.14	1,949	138.32	1,957
Breast - Line Run:	117.00 - 119.00	118.17	-0.11	185	118.28	181
Breast With Ribs:	124.00 - 162.00	144.27	1.99	114	142.28	111
Drumsticks:	34.00 - 56.00	40.01	-2.10	1,011	42.11	1,974
Frames:	4.00 - 8.00	5.90	-0.63	1,960	6.53	1,360
Gizzards and Hearts:	67.00 - 76.00	75.00	0.33	79	74.67	89
Leg quarters - Bulk:	34.00 - 52.00	41.73	-1.98	1,369	43.71	1,849
Legs - Bone-in:	41.00 - 62.00	52.90	1.69	339	51.21	539
Livers:	61.00 - 65.00	62.10	-0.55	86	62.65	104
MSC, 15-20% Fat Content:	25.00 - 27.00	26.14	0.27	285	25.87	612
Tenderloins:	193.00 - 255.00	214.95	8.17	1,007	206.78	1,015
Thighs - B/S:	136.00 - 160.00	143.69	0.15	670	143.54	634
Thighs - Bone-in:	57.00 - 62.00	61.65	-0.16	32	61.81	44
Wings - Whole:	108.00 - 160.00	135.04	9.12	835	125.92	874

Fresh National Boneless Skinless Breast, Jumbo Price - Conventional - FOB

[Major Wholesale Markets – Mexico City](#)
Cents per pound for the week ending August 18, 2023

	Whole Chickens	Breasts	Legs w/ Thighs	Necks, Backs & Wings	Livers/ Gizzards	Hens
RAYON						
Low	170.65	278.67	132.70	82.27	26.54	140.66
High	171.71	289.28	143.32	90.24	29.19	140.66
Mostly	171.18	286.63	140.66	87.58	26.54	140.66
SAN JUAN						
Low	169.86	278.67	132.70	82.27	26.54	140.66
High	171.18	289.28	143.32	90.24	29.19	140.66
Mostly	170.65	283.98	138.01	87.58	26.54	140.66
NEW SAN JUAN						
Low	170.65	281.32	135.35	84.93	26.54	140.66
High	172.24	291.94	145.97	92.89	29.19	140.66
Mostly	171.71	286.63	143.32	87.58	26.54	140.66
BECERRA						
Low	171.18	281.32	138.01	84.93	26.54	140.66
High	172.51	291.94	148.62	92.89	29.19	140.66
Mostly	172.24	289.28	145.97	90.24	26.54	140.66

Young Chickens Slaughtered Under Federal Inspection

Week ending 19-Aug-23

(Preliminary)	Thousands				
	(A) 4.25 lbs. & down	(B) 4.26 - 6.25 lbs.	(C) 6.26 - 7.75 lbs.	(D) 7.76 lbs. & up	Total
Head	26,609	55,950	46,524	40,302	169,385
Avg Live Wgt	3.71	5.15	6.98	9.01	6.35
% of total /1	16%	33%	27%	24%	100%
Comparisons					
Last week	25,611	56,424	50,500	36,164	168,699
Avg Live Wgt	3.47	5.21	7.07	9.11	6.34
% of total /1	15%	33%	30%	21%	100%
Year Ago 2/	21,155	54,242	51,978	43,602	170,977
Avg Live Wgt	3.55	5.10	6.93	8.94	6.44
% of total /1	12%	32%	30%	26%	100%
To date/2023*	905,248	1,656,386	1,529,988	1,385,754	5,477,377
To date/2022*	1,019,265	1,474,337	1,634,417	1,317,351	5,445,370
% Change YTD	-11%	12%	-6%	5%	1%

1/ May not total to 100% due to rounding. 2/ Comparable week.

*Note: Year to-date totals reflect comparable time periods.

Weight Class Description:

(A) This size product is normally marketed bone-in into fast food and food service sectors and may include Cornish hens. (B) This size product is normally marketed into the retail grocery sector in tray pack or bagged forms. (C) This size product is normally marketed either into the retail grocery sector in tray pack and IQF form or is further processed and marketed into various sectors. (D) This size product is normally marketed deboned or as roasters or roasting chicken.

Est. U.S. Fryer Slaughter/Fryer Availability Comparison

Week Ending	Slaughtered	Available*	Percent	Avg Wt
7/15	171.0	167.0	102%	6.41
7/22	167.9	167.5	100%	6.33
7/29	169.2	167.6	101%	6.31
8/5	168.3	168.2	100%	6.26
8/12	170.7	169.4	101%	6.34
8/19	171.4	169.3	101%	6.35
Year to date	5480.9	5513.8	99%	
8/26		169.3		
9/2		168.8		

*Based on chick placements 6 to 7 weeks earlier.

Fast Food and Food Service Sizes

Live weight	RTC WOG's Weight	Head (000)	% of Total Slaughter
3.60 lbs & Down:	Under 2.5 lbs.	5,863	3.46%
3.61 - 3.80:	2.5 - 2.63 lbs.	1,902	1.12%
3.81 - 4.00:	2.63 - 2.75 lbs.	8,511	5.02%
4.01 - 4.25:	2.75 - 2.9 lbs.	10,333	6.10%
Total:		26,609	15.71%

Estimated Slaughter of Broiler-Fryers

	Estimated (1,000)	Actual (1,000)	Avg Wt	Actual (1,000)	Avg Wt
AL	4,099	4,564	4,502	4,479	5.55
AR	4,076	5,008	5,042	4,859	6.21
Delmarva	2,182	2,217	2,102	2,244	7.03
KY-LA-TN	2,660	2,383	2,393	2,405	5.80
MS	1,917	2,516	2,549	2,594	6.19
NC	3,792	3,665	3,718	3,634	8.41
TX	2,677	2,802	2,912	2,867	6.7
Total	21,403	23,156	23,218	23,083	6.53
Mon-Fri	114,693	(A)			112,657 (A)
Saturday	1,178	(included in total for date shown)			207.00

(A) Weekly cumulative for states listed above.

Broiler-fryer slaughter under federal inspection for 25-Aug-23 and 26-Aug-23 is estimated to be 32,573,000 head up 8.68 percent from a week ago and down 8.5 percent from a year ago.

(Last week 29,972,000, last year 35,610,000)

Weekly broiler-fryer slaughter under federal inspection for the week ending

26-Aug-23 is estimated to be 173,891,000 head up 2.66

percent from a week ago, and up 1.77 percent from a year ago.

(Last week 169,385,000, last year 170,865,000) Actual data incorporated when available.

Weekly Miscellaneous Poultry

Chicken- Prices negotiated by first receivers, cents/lb.

Current Week's Trading		
National - Domestic - Fresh - Conventional - Delivered		
-Ice Packed (12/Box)		
Roasters	Price Range	132.00 - 143.25
-Vacuum Packed (6-9 Per Box)		
Roasters	Price Range	136.00 - 148.00
Ducklings (Whole) - 4-5 lbs	Trucklot Pool and Trucklot Quantities, cents/lb., Prices negotiated to first receivers - U.S Grade A - Conventional - Delivered	
	Fresh	Frozen
Long Island	325.00 - 335.00	287.00
Midwest	231.00 - 256.00	221.00 - 241.00
Squabs - Prices for 1 to 10 Boxes, Dollars/Dozen, Wholesale Prices		
New York Area - Domestic - Frozen - Plant Grade - Conventional - Delivered		
	Price Range	
Squabs (Whole) - 11 oz	109.44 - 123.12	
Squabs (Whole) - 13 oz	138.51 - 147.90	
Squabs (Whole) - 15 oz	149.04 - 154.71	

National Fowl Market

Live Spent Heavy Fowl		
Final Prices at Farm Buyer Loading:	Price Range	Wtd Avg
Prices in cents per pound.	6.0 - 11.0	7.77
(Southeast Region broiler breeder hens generally for processing, 7 lbs. and up; under 7 lbs. subject to discount.)		
Southeast Region = AL, FL, GA, KY, MS, NC, SC, TN, AND VA.		
Live Spent Light Fowl		
Majority price (cents/head) for removal: 0-5		
(live hens are predominately egg-layers averaging about 3.5 lbs. live weight per bird.)		
Eastern region = AL, CT, DE, GA, KY, MA, MD, ME, MS, NC, NH, NJ, NY, PA, RI, SC, TN, VA, VT, and WV; North Central = IA, IL, IN, MI, MN, ND, NE, OH, SD, WI; South Central = AR, CO, KS, LA, MO, NM, OK, TX.		

Ready-to-Cook Midwest Region Negotiated Prices to First Receivers
(cents/lb. delivered to first receivers; U.S. Grade A and Plant Grade)

	Price Range
Hens Ice Packed (12 per Box)	80.0 - 86.0
Vacuum Packed (6-9 per Box)	85.0 - 90.0
Midwest region = IL, IN, MI, MO, OH, and WI	

Live Fowl Auctions

Hackettstown, NJ - Tue Aug. 22	Price Range	Avg.
Heavy Fowl each:	3.00 9.00	5.26
per pound:		

Graystone Small Animal, Manheim, PA - Tue Aug. 22

Red Fowl	5-6 lbs:	0.15	0.40	per pound
	4-5 lbs:	0.15	0.40	per pound
Crossbred Fowl	5-9 lbs:	0.50	0.60	per pound

Delmarva Broiler/Fryer Market US Grade A

Date	Production (000) Actual Slaughter	Live Weight
8/18	2,186	6.83
8/17	2,208	6.84
8/16	2,132	7.24
8/15	2,155	7.03
8/14	2,228	7.32
Weekly	8,723	7.11

Cattle/Hog Weekly Slaughter

Under Federal Inspection (in 000's)					
W/E	08/26/23	08/19/23	% chg	08/27/22	% chg
Cattle	626	616	1.02	678 ¹	0.92
Hogs	2,500	2,414	1.04	2,412 ¹	1.04
¹ Actual data incorporated when available.					
Totals adjusted to reflect USDA, NASS revisions.					

[Broiler Hatchery](#)

Broiler-Type Eggs Set in the United States Up Slightly

Hatcheries in the United States weekly program set 246 million eggs in incubators during the week ending August 19, 2023, up slightly from a year ago. Average hatchability for chicks hatched during the week in the United States was 79.5 percent. Average hatchability is calculated by dividing chicks hatched during the week by eggs set three-weeks earlier.

Broiler-Type Chicks Placed in the United States Down Slightly

Broiler growers in the United States weekly program placed 191 million chicks for meat production during the week ending August 19, 2023, down slightly from a year ago. Cumulative placements from the week ending January 7, 2023 through August 19, 2023 for the United States were 6.20 billion. Cumulative placements were down slightly from the same period a year earlier.

State	Broiler-Type Eggs Set,		Broiler-Type Chicks Placed,	
	19 Selected States and United States			
	Week Ending			
	Aug 12, 2023	Aug 19, 2023	Aug 12, 2023	Aug 19, 2023
	(1,000 eggs)	(1,000 eggs)	(1,000 chicks)	(1,000 chicks)
AL	35,583	35,856	25,901	26,348
AR	24,864	24,597	22,612	20,640
DE	5,578	5,721	5,310	4,793
FL	1,225	1,225	1,236	1,304
GA	36,887	37,183	29,077	27,681
KY	8,101	8,021	6,527	6,867
LA	3,517	3,517	2,856	2,526
MD	8,066	8,065	5,493	6,270
MS	17,303	17,237	14,109	13,480
MO	9,658	9,769	5,524	5,966
NC	24,186	24,101	19,104	19,655
OK	7,291	7,373	3,911	5,417
PA	7,485	7,284	4,901	4,905
SC	5,765	5,968	5,251	4,890
TX	18,264	18,647	14,884	14,385
VA	6,317	5,789	5,414	4,791
CA, TN, & WV	13,579	13,520	11,056	11,481
Other States	12,482	12,527	9,632	9,636
United States	246,151	246,400	192,798	191,035

Source: USDA, NASS

[US/Canadian Live Poultry Slaughtered Under Inspection](#)

Week ending	19-Aug-23		
U.S. Fowl Slaughtered Domestically			
	Light Hens	Heavy Hens	Total Hens
	----- Thousands -----		
Head	739	1,968	2,707
Head sltr Comparisons			
Last Week	665	1,917	2,582
Same week yr ago	637	1,784	2,421
To-date/2022*	100,660	218,674	319,334
To-date/2021*	99,811	215,743	315,554

U.S. Fowl Slaughtered in Canada

	Light Hens	Heavy Hens	Total Hens
	----- Thousands -----		
Head	162	0	162
Head sltr Comparisons			
Last Week	0	0	0
Same week yr ago	84	0	84
To-date/2022*	12,015	174	12,189
To-date/2021*	14,528	162	14,690

Data Source: CFIA, as compiled by AAFC, Poultry Section

Total U.S. Fowl Slaughtered in the U.S. and Canada

	Light Hens	Heavy Hens	Total Hens
	----- Thousands -----		
Head	901	1,968	2,869
Head sltr Comparisons			
Last Week	665	1,917	2,582
Same week yr ago	721	1,784	2,505
To-date/2022*	112,675	218,848	331,523
To-date/2021*	114,339	215,905	330,244

*Note: Year to-date totals reflect comparable time periods.

[Weekly Cold Storage Holdings](#) -

~in Selected Centers, Includes Government Stocks in Thousands of Pounds~

Processed other Poultry			
8/21/2023	8/1/2023	Change from First of the Month in Total Pounds	% Change from First of the Month
85,154	86,762	-1,608	-2%

Cold Storage Holdings - Pacific Coast

	8/21/2023	08/14/2023	08/22/2022
Pacific w/out Denver:	6,781	6,862	10,940
Los Angeles:	535	520	526

[Fresh Beef Choice Cuts](#)

FOB Negotiated	# of Trades	Total lbs.	Price Range	Wtd Avg
112A 3 Rib, ribeye, bnls, heavy	24	57,318	1,132.72 - 1,185.00	1,159.48
168 3 Round, top inside round	4	27,162	352.50 - 375.00	362.89
180 3 Loin, strip, bnls, 0x1	30	108,172	702.72 - 809.37	745.33

GB - Steer/Heifer Source - 10 Pound Chub Basis- Coarse & Fine Grind

Ground Beef 81%	7	22,869	276.00 - 305.00	287.18
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[Fresh Pork Cuts](#)

FOB Negotiated	Kilo lbs.	Price Range	Wtd Avg
Loin			
1/8 Trimmed Loin VAC	1,857	103.57 - 192.00	118.74
Bnls CC Strap-on	2,006	119.00 - 199.50	154.81
Butt			
1/8 Trim Steak Ready Butt Vac	370	114.30 - 136.05	122.41
Sparerib			
Trmrd Sparerib - MED	2,102	100.00 - 152.45	123.21

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